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SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY, NIŠ**

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8. NOISE ANNOYANCE IN RESIDENTIAL AREAS IN NOVI SAD, 2012-2016

Živadinović Emil, Bijelović S., Jevtić M., Dragić N., Lalović Ž., Milošević S.
Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Objectives: The aim of paper is to quantify the annoyance of the population in the residential areas in the City of Novi Sad (RA-NS) using environmental noise data, in the first place by road traffic noise. It is important for perceiving the noise impact on the human health.

Methods: Public Health Institute of Vojvodina taken 26 24-hour noise measurements on one measuring spot in RA-NS, during 2012 – 2016.

Results: Daily noise indicator (L_{day}) ranged from 54,6 dB to 70,1 dB, evening noise indicator ($L_{evening}$) from 51,2 dB to 60,0 dB, night noise indicator (L_{night}) from 47,2 dB / 50,7 dB, while total noise indicator (L_{den}) ranged from 58,0 dB to 67,6 dB. Relative to limit values, there were increased 92% of L_{day} , 38% of $L_{evening}$ and 100% of L_{night} . Relative to results, the percentage of highly annoyed population (%HA) amounts 11% during the day and 6% during the night, while prevalence of population highly annoyed (PHA) is 11% - more specifically in the range 9,2-33,9%.

Conclusion: The results confirm that urban noise annoying population in the residential areas. and, in conclusion, that fact is the challenge, the problem and the topic for the public health system.

Keywords: noise, annoyance, population